

Nonlinear Fresnel Zone Plate Reflector

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Abstract—This paper describes a nonlinear Fresnel zone plate reflector designed to operate at 2.8GHz. The alternating Fresnel zones of the reflector are made from two different nonlinear metamaterials: one that reflects like a short circuit at low incident power levels and another that reflects like an open circuit. Both metamaterials transition from highly reflective to highly transparent as the incident power increases. Additionally, as the metamaterials transition to their transparent state the phase difference between their reflection coefficients decreases substantially, causing the reflector to lose its focusing capabilities. In this way, the field observed at the focus is reduced both as a consequence of the metamaterials becoming transparent as well as the reflector defocusing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear metamaterials have opened a new design space for electrical engineers by allowing them to tailor power-dependent electromagnetic properties. These media have already found applications in high-power limiting [1] and field enhancement [2]. Here nonlinear behavior is introduced to a Fresnel zone plate reflector [3] as an analog form of automatic gain control. Traditionally, the Fresnel zone plate is a planar focusing element that focuses energy by diffraction using alternating opaque and transparent concentric regions. Here the same effect is achieved by alternating the reflection coefficient phase of the concentric regions between 180° and 0° .

Two different nonlinear metamaterial unit cell designs are used to create the alternating Fresnel zones. One unit cell is designed to produce a low power reflection coefficient of $\Gamma \approx -1$ and is referred to as the “short” cell, while the other unit cell is designed to achieve $\Gamma \approx 1$ for low incident power as is designated as the “open” unit cell. This design focuses the reflected energy to a point when the incident power is low, however, as the power increases, the magnitudes of both unit cells’ reflection coefficient decreases reducing the energy directed to the focus and increasing the power transmitted through the lens. In addition to decreasing in amplitude as power increases, the reflection coefficient phase of the open unit cell transitions from 0° to 180° . This results in the defocusing of the Fresnel zone plate and, as a result, a further decrease in the power concentrated at the focus.

Adding this nonlinear capability to Fresnel zone plate reflector antennas can reduce the likelihood of receivers being saturated or damaged as a result of excessive incident power. This allows the receiver’s dynamic range to be used more efficiently as well, by ensuring that the antenna gain is highest when necessary but automatically reduced as dictated by the incident power. The remainder of the paper will describe the

Fig. 1. Two different nonlinear metamaterial unit cells.

design of the two unit cells and conclude with the simulated behavior of the lens at high and low power levels.

II. NONLINEAR METAMATERIAL UNIT CELL DESIGN

The nonlinear metamaterial unit cells that comprise the Fresnel reflector (shown in Fig. 1) are similar to an earlier nonlinear metamaterial structure that was designed to transition from reflective to transparent as the incident power increased [4]. The unit cells consist of two printed circuit boards, referred to as the electric and magnetic boards. The electric board supports a meandered, cut-wire metallic trace, which predominantly affects the permittivity response. A connected split-ring-resonator structure is printed on the magnetic board, which is primarily governs the permeability response but has a significant effect on the permittivity as well. The gaps in the connected split-ring resonators and the cut-wire traces are loaded with either lumped capacitors or unbiased Skyworks SMV-2201 Schottky diodes which result in Lorentzian responses for both the effective permittivity and permeability at low power. Sufficiently high incident power activates the diodes, shorting out any gaps that the diodes span. In the case of the diodes loading the connected split rings, increasing power results in the effective permeability transitioning from the Lorentzian response to a flat diamagnetic response. When the diodes load the cut wires, the effective permittivity changes from a Lorentzian response to a Drude response.

To ensure that the reflection coefficient phases of the low-power state are nearly 0° for the open unit cell and 180° for the short unit cell, one can design the material parameters to give an effective short circuit or an effective open circuit based on

Fig. 2. Reflection coefficient magnitudes of the metamaterial unit cells in both the low-power (diodes off) and high-power (diodes on) states.

the expression for the material impedance: $\eta = \sqrt{\mu/\epsilon}$. Since infinite values are not physically realizable, the best way to achieve an effective short circuit is by forcing the effective permeability to 0. Consequently, the magnetic plasma frequency of the short cell was designed to match the operating frequency of 2.8GHz at low power. To avoid an impedance match by having the permittivity near zero as well, the electric plasma frequency was pushed far from the operating frequency, up to 3.9GHz. At high power levels the diodes on the electric board activate, moving the electric plasma frequency of the short cell down to 2.9GHz. This creates two impedance matches: a negative-index match at 2.5GHz and a positive index match at 3.0GHz. At the operating frequency of 2.8GHz the reflection coefficients are $\Gamma_{short}^{LP} = 0.90\angle 173^\circ$ and $\Gamma_{short}^{HP} = 0.22\angle 141^\circ$ for low and high power, respectively.

Using a similar design strategy, the desired open circuit behavior can be realized by forcing the effective permittivity to 0. To achieve this, the electric plasma frequency of the open cell was designed to match the operating frequency of 2.8GHz at low power with the magnetic plasma frequency at 3.7GHz. Since both the magnetic and electric elements are loaded with diodes in the open cell design (see Fig. 1(b)), both the permittivity and permeability responses change with high incident power. The magnetic plasma frequency is eliminated because the permeability now exhibits a flat diamagnetic response which is positive for all frequencies. The electric plasma frequency moves down to 2.4GHz, resulting in an impedance match at 2.7GHz. The open unit cell design yields reflection coefficients of $\Gamma_{open}^{LP} = 0.84\angle 2.6^\circ$ and $\Gamma_{open}^{HP} = 0.18\angle -179^\circ$ at 2.8GHz for low and high power, respectively.

III. FRESNEL ZONE PLATE REFLECTOR SIMULATIONS

After designing the two unit cell types, the spacing of Fresnel zones can now be determined in order to produce a focus in a desired position, which in this case was $5\lambda_0/4$ at 2.8GHz (13.4cm) in front of the reflector. From the center outward, the Fresnel zone plate reflector consists of thirteen short cells in the first zone, seven open cells in the second zone, seven short cells in the third zone and four open cells in the fourth zone. The zones are symmetric about the center and are depicted in

a parallel-plate-waveguide environment in Fig. 3. The entire Fresnel zone plate reflector was simulated by homogenizing the nonlinear metamaterials into a slab with effective material parameters extracted from the S-parameters of the unit cells and exciting the structure with a $-\hat{x}$ -propagating plane wave.

Fig. 3. Normalized electric field plots for the Fresnel reflector with a $-\hat{x}$ -propagating incident plane wave.

At low-powers, a clear focus can be seen in Fig. 3(a), with minimal field propagating through the reflector. However, at high powers, the majority of the plane wave is transmitted through the reflector, as shown in Fig. 3(b). Additionally, what little power is reflected is not concentrated at the focus. In this way, the power received by an antenna located at the focus of such a reflector would be reduced both as a consequence of the metamaterial becoming transparent and the defocusing of the Fresnel zone plate. Having two methods by which to control the power directed to the receiver improves an engineer's capabilities of attenuating excessively strong signals and enhancing weak ones.

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